

Review

Effectiveness and Methodology of Wet-cupping for Low Back Pain – A Preliminary Systematic Review of Randomized Controlled Trials.

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Abstract

Background: Low back pain is the leading cause of disability globally, affecting more than 80% of individuals over a lifetime and incurring significant healthcare and economic burdens. European guidelines recommend non-pharmacological interventions, including traditional therapies. Wet-cupping, a practice with deep historical roots in various medical traditions, is being revisited as a potential adjunctive therapy for Low back pain management.

Objective: To evaluate the effectiveness and methodologies of wet-cupping therapy for low back pain based on current evidence from randomized controlled trials (RCTs).

Methods: A preliminary systematic literature search was conducted using PubMed, EuropePMC, and SciELO up to May 2025 for RCTs involving wet-cupping in Low back pain. Studies were included if they assessed wet-cupping as an intervention for human subjects with low back pain and reported pain outcomes. Five eligible RCTs comprising 460 participants were reviewed. Interventions included traditional *Hijamah* and traditional Chinese medicine-based wet-cupping.

Results: Both *Hijamah* and traditional Chinese medicine-based wet-cupping demonstrated significant short-term and, in some cases, long-term reductions in pain and disability scores. Studies comparing wet-cupping to standard or no treatment reported superior outcomes in the cupping groups. In addition, some studies showed a reduction in analgesic use. Treatment protocols varied, particularly in cupping technique and site selection limiting direct comparability.

Conclusions: Wet-cupping appears to be a promising complementary therapy for low back pain, with evidence supporting its effectiveness in improving pain and functional outcomes. Both traditional *Hijamah* and acupoint-based approaches yielded comparable benefits. However, methodological heterogeneity across studies calls for further high-quality, standardized research to confirm its clinical utility and long-term efficacy.

Keywords: Low Back Pain; Wet-Cupping; *Hijamah*; Traditional Chinese Medicine; Complementary Therapy; Randomized Controlled Trial; Pain Management.

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1. Introduction

Low back pain is a significant global health issue, recognized as the leading cause of disability worldwide. At any given time, approximately 7.5% of the global population

experiences low back pain, and over a lifetime, more than 80% of individuals will be affected. The impact extends to emergency services, with low back pain accounting for 4% of all emergency department visits ¹.

The prevalence of low back pain also places a substantial burden on primary care; around 20% of those experiencing low back pain consult their general practitioner annually ². For example, within the UK's National Health Service (NHS), back pain is a major contributor to workforce issues, responsible for a staggering 40% of all sickness absences. Economically, low back pain costs the UK economy an estimated £10 billion each year ².

Recent European clinical practice guidelines show a strong consensus on evidence-based treatment recommendations for patients experiencing low back pain ³. These guidelines predominantly advocate for a wide array of non-pharmacological treatment options. Therefore, it has become important to explore non-pharmacological therapies to address or complement the treatment of low back pain.

Cupping has been used differently in the traditional medicines of various civilizations ⁴. However, a common objective was to promote the extraction of toxic substances from the body by producing negative pressure inside a cup or a similar hollow object ^{5,6}. In particular, wet-cupping is a therapeutic process involving the initiation of superficial bleeding from small vessels or their branches, primarily within the skin and muscles, to decrease congestion in the area where cups are applied and to release toxic matter accumulated close to the skin ⁷⁻⁹.

Its ancient practice has been recorded for thousands of years. One of the earliest mention was found in the Egyptian Ebers Papyrus (1550 B.C.) ¹⁰. As well, with therapeutic records reaching back to the early first millennium, cupping is a long-standing practice in traditional Chinese medicine ⁴. In ancient Greece, its value was similarly recognized, with Hippocrates advocating for the technique to address diverse ailments ¹¹.

In light of wet-cupping's historical prominence and persistent clinical application, this study seeks to provide a preliminary analysis of its efficacy and methodological approaches for managing low back pain.

2. Methods

2.1. Search Strategy

A database search was performed to identify RCTs assessing the efficacy of wet cupping in the treatment of low back pain. The search strategy was implemented across several electronic databases, including PubMed, EuropePMC, and SciELO from database inception to May 2025. The search strategy employed the following operators: ("low back pain") AND (wet-cupping) AND (randomized controlled trial).

2.2. Eligibility Criteria

This review included RCTs investigating the effect of wet-cupping on low-back pain. Studies were considered for inclusion if they: (1) involved human participants with a diagnosis of low back pain; (2) were published in English, Chinese, Spanish, French, or Portuguese; (3) evaluated any form of wet-cupping as an intervention; and (4) reported pain outcomes. Studies involving animal subjects or lacking proper intervention were excluded.

3. Results

Forty-seven records were identified after the database searches. After removing 5 duplicates, 42 records were screened. Thereafter, 36 were excluded for various reasons (Figure 1). All six remaining studies were retrieved and their full-text was assessed.

Ultimately, five studies met the inclusion criteria and were included in the systematic review. Figure 1 further provides detailed information about the selection process.

Figure 1. Flowchart of the studies selection.

Five RCTs involving 460 participants were included in this analysis. The studies evaluated the use of wet cupping for low back pain, with samples ranging from 37 to 180 participants. Mainly, two methodologies of wet cupping were studied, with 3 studies assessing the effects of traditional *Hijamah*¹²⁻¹⁴ and 3 studies assessing traditional Chinese medicine-based cupping^{12,15,16}, one of which as a comparator¹².

All studies used a single-comparator methodology. Specifically, standard treatment was used in 2 studies^{13,14}, no treatment was used in 2 other studies^{15,16} and traditional Chinese medicine-based cupping in 1 study¹².

Table 1 provides a summary of the characteristics of the included studies.

Table 1. Characteristics of the five included studies.

Study	Sample	Duration	Cupping technique	Comparator	Outcome measures
Al-Eidi <i>et al.</i> ¹²	70	2 weeks	Traditional <i>Hijamah</i>	Traditional Chinese medicine-based cupping	Validated Arabic version of the NRS, PPI, and ODQ.
Mardani-Kivi <i>et al.</i> ¹³	180	4 weeks	Traditional <i>Hijamah</i>	Conventional treatment	ODI and VAS

Farhadi et al. ¹⁴	98	3 months	Traditional Hijamah	Standard treatment	PPI, ODI, and MQS.
AlBedah et al. ¹⁵	80	2 weeks	Traditional Chinese medicine-based cupping	No treatment	NRS, PPI, ODQ, and Numbers of acetaminophen tablets taken
Kim et al. ¹⁶	32	2 weeks	Traditional Chinese medicine-based cupping	Wait-list	NRS, PPI, ODQ, and Numbers of acetaminophen tablets taken

NRS – Numeric Rating Scale; PPI - Present Pain Intensity; ODQ - Oswestry Disability Questionnaire; ODI - Oswestry Disability Index; VAS – Visual Analogue Scale; MQS - Medication Quantification Scale

4. Effectiveness of wet-cupping for low-back pain

The reviewed studies consistently support the effectiveness of wet cupping therapy in alleviating low back pain. However, methodological differences and variations in outcome measures only allow few direct comparisons between studies.

4.1. Traditional Hijamah versus Traditional Chinese medicine-based cupping

In the study of Al-Eidi *et al.* ¹², both the traditional *Hijamah* and traditional Chinese medicine-based cupping led to significant reductions in pain and disability scores (NRS, PPI, and ODQ) immediately after the intervention. These improvements were maintained at Day 7 and Day 14 post-intervention ($p < 0.001$), indicating sustained short-term benefits using either technique.

As well, there were no statistically significant differences between the two cupping techniques at any post-treatment time point (immediately, Day 7, or Day 14), suggesting that both techniques are equally effective in reducing low back pain.

4.2. Cupping versus standard treatment

The studies of Mardani-Kivi *et al.* ¹³ and Farhadi *et al.* ¹⁴ assessed the efficacy of cupping in comparison with usual treatment.

In study of Mardani-Kivi *et al.* ¹³, both the wet cupping and conventional treatment groups showed progressive improvements in pain intensity over time. However, a significant advantage in the wet-cupping group emerged at the 3-month follow-up ($P < 0.05$) and became more pronounced by 6 months ($P < 0.05$), indicating a sustained therapeutic benefit. This trend was mirrored in functional outcomes, with significantly better Oswestry Disability Index (ODI) scores observed in the wet cupping group at the final follow-up ($P < 0.05$).

Similarly, the study by Farhadi *et al.* ¹⁴ demonstrated that, at 3 months, the wet cupping group experienced significantly greater reductions in pain intensity compared to the control group (mean difference = 2.17; 95% CI: 1.72–2.60; $p < 0.01$), along with a significant improvement in disability (mean difference = 14.99; 95% CI: 11.18–18.82; $p < 0.01$). As well, this study also reported a significant reduction in medication usage (mean difference = 6.55; 95% CI: 3.60–9.50; $p < 0.01$) among participants receiving wet-cupping. Moreover, these differences remained statistically significant after adjustment for potential confounding variables, including age, gender, and duration of low back pain, reinforcing the independent therapeutic effect of the intervention ($p < 0.01$).

These findings suggest that wet cupping not only provides clinically meaningful improvements in pain and function but may also reduce reliance on pharmacological pain management. While study of Mardani-Kivi *et al.* ¹³ highlights the long-term benefits observed up to six months, Farhadi *et al.* ¹⁴ strengthens the evidence base through detailed effect size reporting and adjusted analyses, thereby supporting the robustness and generalizability of wet-cupping as a treatment approach.

4.3. Cupping versus no treatment

Two studies compared wet-cupping with no treatment for low back pain.

Both studies ^{15,16} assessed pain intensity, pain perception, and disability following wet cupping interventions. The study by AlBedah *et al.* ¹⁵ reported statistically significant improvements across all measured outcomes, including reductions in Numeric Rating Scale (NRS) scores (29.2 vs. 57.9), Present Pain Intensity (PPI) scores (1.17 vs. 2.3), and Oswestry Disability Questionnaire (ODQ) scores (19.6 vs. 35.4), with $p = 0.0001$ for all comparisons. Moreover, the benefits were sustained for at least two weeks post-intervention, suggesting a lasting therapeutic effect.

In contrast, the study by Kim *et al.* ¹⁶ found a statistically significant reduction only in PPI scores in the wet cupping group (-1.2 vs. -0.2 ; $p < 0.01$), while improvements in NRS (-16.0 vs. -9.1 ; $p = 0.52$) and ODQ scores (-5.60 vs. -1.8 ; $p = 0.14$) did not reach statistical significance. Both studies noted lower acetaminophen consumption in the wet-cupping groups, though this difference was not statistically significant.

Together, these findings suggest that wet cupping may exert a positive effect on both subjective pain perception and functional status, with more robust evidence demonstrated in the study of AlBedah *et al.* ¹⁵. The trend toward reduced medication use further supports its potential as an adjunctive treatment. However, discrepancies in statistical significance across studies indicate the need for larger, well-controlled trials to confirm these outcomes and elucidate the mechanisms underpinning the therapeutic effects of wet cupping.

5. Cupping treatment methodologies

The reviewed studies demonstrated considerable heterogeneity in both the type and application protocols of cupping therapy. Broadly, two primary approaches were utilized: Traditional *Hijamah* ¹²⁻¹⁴ and wet-cupping based on acupoint selection ^{12,15,16}.

5.1. Traditional Hijamah methodology ¹²⁻¹⁴

The employed protocols reflect methods rooted in traditional Iranian medicine, with a focus on specific anatomical sites (e.g., interscapular area, sacral region, and calf). The procedures often involve (1) fixed anatomical locations rather than individualized acupoint selection, (2) multiple stages or sessions (as in the study of Farhadi *et al.* ¹⁴ and Table 2), (3) Use of scarification followed by bloodletting, (4) Variable cup sizes based on patient anatomy or experts' preference, and (5) retention times typically around 5 minutes with repeated cycles.

Regarding the treatment stages, some differences can be observed, For example in contrast to Farhadi *et al.* ¹⁴, Mardani-Kivi *et al.* ¹³ used two treatment locations (on the interscapular area and on the sacrum area) and Al-Eidi *et al.* ¹² only one treatment location (low back area), which may have influenced the achieved results.

Despite the common traditional basis, procedural steps vary slightly. Table 3 presents a common *Hijamah* procedure.

Table 2. The 3 phases of treatment based on Farhadi *et al.* ¹⁴.

Wet-cupping phases	Schematic
(a) Phase 1 (day = 0): between the two scapulas, opposite to T1 – T3 Scapular spine,	
(b) Phase 2 (day = 3): the sacrum area, between the lumbar vertebrae and the coccyx bone.	

(c) Phase 3 (day = 6): the calf area, in the middle surface of gastrocnemius muscle.

Note: The calf area is treated based on the experienced low back pain. If the back pain was unilateral, the ipsilateral calf should be treated. If the back pain is bilateral, both calf areas should be treated.

Table 3. *Hijamah* procedure steps and descriptions.

Step	Procedure Description
1	Site selection: Identify specific anatomical sites (e.g., interscapular area, sacral region, or calf) based on traditional recommendations or the patient's pain location.
2	Primary suction: Place sterile cups on the selected sites and apply negative pressure using a manual or electric pump to initiate suction. Retain cups for 3–5 minutes.
3	Cup removal: Remove the cups carefully after the initial suction phase.
4	Scarification: Perform superficial skin incisions (typically 3–6 lines per site, ~3 mm long and 0.5 mm deep) using a sterile surgical blade (e.g., size 15–21), following the “multiple superficial incisions” technique.
5	Secondary suction and bloodletting: Reapply the cups over the incised areas and re-establish suction to allow capillary blood to accumulate. Leave in place for 3–5 minutes or until sufficient blood is collected.
6	Repeat bloodletting (optional): In some protocols, the suction and bloodletting step is repeated up to two more times without re-scarification, depending on the patient's condition and blood flow.
	Cup removal: Gently remove the cups and discard used materials appropriately.
	Wound care: Clean the area with antiseptic solution and apply sterile dressing to prevent infection.
	Post-procedure advice: Advise the patient to rest, stay hydrated, avoid strenuous activity, and keep the cupped area clean for at least 24 hours.

5.2. Wet-Cupping with Acupoint Selection ^{12,15,16}.

The included studies using traditional Chinese medicine-based wet-cupping follow a more standardized and evidence-based acupuncture framework, selecting bilateral BL23, BL24, and BL25 based on (1) pain palpation and patient-reported sensitivity, (2) WHO Guidelines for Acupuncture Point Location ¹⁷ (Table 4) and (3) practitioner experience and training ¹⁶.

Table 4. Traditional Chinese medicine-based wet-cupping points according to the World Health Organization ¹⁷.

Acupoint	Descriptive point localization	Visual point localization
BL23: Shenshu 腎俞(俞)	In the lumbar region, at the same level as the inferior border of the spinous process of the second lumbar vertebra (L2), 1.5 B-cun lateral to the posterior median line.	
BL24: Qihai 氣(气,氣)海(海)俞(俞)	In the lumbar region, at the same level as the inferior border of the spinous process of the third lumbar vertebra (L3), 1.5 B-cun lateral to the posterior median line.	
BL25: Dachangshu 大腸俞(俞)	In the lumbar region, at the same level as the inferior border of the spinous process of the fourth lumbar vertebra (L4), 1.5 B-cun lateral to the posterior median line.	

The treatment protocols involved 3 sessions per week for 2 weeks, with treatment points tailored to individual pain sites. While technically similar, Kim *et al.*¹⁶ details practitioner qualifications, enhancing reproducibility and methodological rigor.

The steps used in the treatments are represented in Table 5.

Table 5. Traditional Chinese medicine-based wet-cupping treatment steps based on the included studies.

Step	Procedure Description
1	Treatment point selection: At each session, 2 treatment points were selected from the bilateral BL23, BL24, and BL25 acupoints (i.e., four possible points total). Note: The two most painful points would be identified using manual palpation and patient feedback. If no point was sensitive or painful, bilateral BL25 was used by default.
2	Scarification: Using lancet needles, shallow punctures were made at each selected point to a depth of 2 mm to enable bloodletting.
3	Cup attachment: Sterile vacuum cups were applied directly over the punctured sites.
4	Suction initiation: A manual pump was used to create maximum negative pressure within the cups, facilitating blood flow.
5	Retention phase: Cups were left in place for 5 minutes to allow for sufficient blood extraction.
6	Cup removal: The exhaust valve was opened to release pressure, and the cups were then carefully removed.

5.3. Implications for clinical practice and future research

The findings from this review provide preliminary but encouraging evidence that wet-cupping therapy may serve as an effective adjunctive treatment for patients suffering from low back pain. Across the five included RCTs, significant improvements were observed in pain intensity, functional disability, and, in some cases, reduced reliance on pharmacological agents such as acetaminophen. Notably, both traditional *Hijamah* and traditional Chinese medicine-based cupping methodologies demonstrated comparable efficacy, suggesting a level of therapeutic consistency despite procedural variation.

From a clinical standpoint, wet-cupping may offer a viable non-pharmacological option that aligns with current European guidelines recommending multimodal and conservative management of low back pain. Given the growing concerns surrounding opioid and analgesic overuse, especially in chronic pain conditions¹⁸, wet-cupping could contribute meaningfully to reducing medication dependency and enhancing patient-reported outcomes.

Furthermore, the documented benefits in both acute and subacute settings, particularly the sustained improvements reported at 3- and 6-month follow-ups, underscore its potential for long-term symptom relief. Clinicians may consider incorporating cupping as a complementary modality, particularly for patients seeking culturally congruent or less invasive interventions. However, appropriate training, standardization of techniques, and attention to hygiene and safety protocols are essential for its integration into mainstream practice.

Despite these promising outcomes, future research remains imperative to address the current limitations. The heterogeneity observed in intervention protocols, treatment durations, and outcome measures difficult direct comparison and synthesis of results. Larger, multicenter RCTs with rigorous methodology, consistent acupoint protocols, and long-term follow-up are required to validate the effectiveness and safety of wet-cupping across diverse patient populations.

Moreover, mechanistic studies exploring the physiological basis of cupping, such as its impact on inflammatory mediators, muscle perfusion, and neuromodulation, would be valuable in elucidating how this ancient practice exerts measurable clinical effects. Finally, cost-effectiveness analyses and qualitative studies assessing patient satisfaction and cultural acceptance will further inform policy decisions and health system adoption.

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, while wet-cupping shows promise as an evidence-informed, low-cost adjunct for low back pain, its incorporation into routine care should be guided by future high-quality trials, standardized protocols, and interdisciplinary collaboration between traditional and modern healthcare practitioners.

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